

Effect of solvents on extraction of various phytochemicals and antioxidant activity in carrot (*Daucus carota* L.)

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Abstract : In the present study, an attempt was made to investigate the efficiency of three solvents viz. acetone, ethanol and water for extraction of total phenolics, flavonoids, carotenoids and ascorbic acid from carrot (*Daucus carota* L.). These extracts were also evaluated for free radical scavenging activity by DPPH method and antioxidant activity by β -carotene bleaching method. The results revealed that ethanolic extract of carrot showed the highest extract yield i.e. 6.23 g/100 g. Water extract contained the highest amount of total phenolics (0.30 mg GAE/g fw) and ascorbic acid (4.92 mg/100 g fw) whereas acetone extract contained the highest amount of flavonoids (0.31 mg CE/g fw) and carotenoids (3.46 mg/100 g fw). DPPH free radical scavenging activity of the carrot extracts varied widely and it increased with increase of concentration levels. Water extract exhibited the highest DPPH free radical scavenging activity with IC₅₀ value (15.8 mg/mL) and antioxidant activity (53.5%) by β -carotene bleaching method.

Keywords : *Daucus carota*, phenolics, flavonoids, ascorbic acid, carotenoids, antioxidant activity.

Introduction

Plant secondary metabolites are the interest subject of research, but their extraction as part of phytochemical or biological investigations presents specific challenges that must be addressed throughout the solvent extraction process¹. During the extraction of plant material, it is important to minimize interference from compounds that may co-extract with the desired phytochemicals, and to avoid contamination of the extract as well as to prevent decomposition of metabolites or artifact formation as a result of extraction conditions. Extraction of phytochemicals from a plant material can be carried out using different solvents because of diversity of chemical nature and often unique distribution of these compounds in the plant matrix^{2,3}. Various solvents are being frequently used for extraction of plant antioxidant compounds. However, the extract yields and antioxidant efficacy of the resulting extracts is strongly affected by polarity of the solvent as well as the chemical nature of the extracted compounds^{3,4}.

Carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) belongs to the family Umbelliferae and is one of the important root vegetable rich in bioactive compounds like carotenoids, dietary fibres, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, β -carotene, soluble dry matter, ascorbic acid and sugars⁵. Major phenols in carrot include chlorogenic, caffeic and *p*-hydroxy benzoic acids along with numerous cinnamic acid derivatives⁶. Quercetin, kaempferol, apigenin and luteolin are the major flavonoids found in carrot. Worldwide carrots have purplish, yellow, red, orange and black colour. β -Carotene constitutes a large portion (60–80%) of the carotenoids in carrots, followed by α -carotene (10–40%), lutein (1–5%) and the other carotenoids in minor quantities (0.1–1%)⁷. Survey of the literature revealed that no systematic work has been done on the effect of solvents on extraction of phytochemicals from carrot and their antioxidant activity. Therefore, the objective of present study was to evaluate the efficacy of solvents towards extracting phytochemicals from carrot and also to assess their antioxidant potential.

Results and discussion

Moisture content and extract yield :

The moisture content of carrot was found to be 89.09%. Extract yield of carrot extracts varied widely and is shown in Table 1. Ethanol extract showed the highest extract yield (6.23 g/100 g) followed by acetone extract (4.03 g/100 g) and water extract (1.89 g/100 g). Our finding is in agreement with previous investigation which reported that the ethanolic extracts of shrubs (*P. tridentatum*, *C. scoparius* and *Erica* spp.) presented higher extract yields than the aqueous extracts⁸.

Total phenolic content :

Total phenolic content of carrot extracts in three solvents varied widely. On fresh weight basis, water extract of carrot contained the highest total phenolic content i.e. 0.30 mg GAE/g fwb followed by ethanol (0.12 mg GAE/g fwb) and acetone (0.06 mg GAE/g fwb) extracts (Table 1). Similar trend was observed on dry weight basis (Table 2). Other research workers have also reported similar findings. The total phenolics content in different cultivars of carrot grown under North Indian conditions have been reported to be from 0.09 to 0.18 mg/g fwb and from 0.98 to 1.94 mg/g dwb⁹. Water extract of Rang Chuet have been reported to contain highest phenolic content followed by ethanol and acetone extracts¹⁰. Similarly, the phenolic content of the mushroom samples extracted with water and hot water were much higher than those extracted with acetone and ethanol¹¹.

Flavonoids content :

Flavonoids content of carrot extracts in three solvents

varied widely. On fresh weight basis, acetone extract of carrot contained the highest flavonoids content i.e. 0.31 mg CE/g fwb followed by ethanol (0.21 mg CE/g fwb) and water (0.10 mg CE/g fwb) extracts (Table 1). Similar trend was observed on dry weight basis (Table 2). Total flavonoid content in carrot has been reported to be 0.27 mg CE/g on fresh weight basis by other research workers¹². Acetone extract of *C. papaya* seeds showed maximum flavonoid content followed by ethanol extract and water extracted least amount of flavonoids¹³. Similarly, acetone was the best solvent for extracting flavonoids from bitter melon followed by ethanol and water¹⁴.

Ascorbic acid content :

Ascorbic acid content in carrot was found to be highest in water extract (4.92 mg/100 g fwb) followed by ethanol (1.86 mg/100 g fwb) and acetone (0.83 mg/100 g fwb) extracts (Table 1). Similar trend was observed on dry weight basis (Table 2). Some other research workers have also reported the same. The ascorbic acid content in different carrot cultivars ranged from 1.4 to 5.8 mg/100 g fwb¹⁵. The solubility of L-(+)-ascorbic acid in water and methanol is high when compared with ethanol, propan-2-ol, acetone, acetonitrile, ethyl acetate and tetrahydrofuran¹⁶. In present studies, ascorbic acid in water extract of carrot are found to be higher in comparison to ethanol and acetone extracts which may be due to high solubility of ascorbic acid in water in comparison to ethanol and acetone.

Carotenoids content :

Carotenoids content in carrot was found to be highest

Table 1. Extract yield, total phenolics, flavonoids, ascorbic acid and carotenoids contents of carrot extracts prepared using different solvents

Solvent	Extract yield (g/100 g)	Total phenolics content (mg GAE/g fwb)	Flavonoids content (mg CE/g fwb)	Ascorbic acid content (mg/100 g fwb)	Carotenoids content (mg/100 g fwb)
Acetone	4.03 ± 0.04	0.06 ± 0.01	0.31 ± 0.01	0.83 ± 0.05	3.46 ± 0.11
Ethanol	6.23 ± 0.03	0.12 ± 0.01	0.21 ± 0.01	1.86 ± 0.05	0.56 ± 0.02
Water	1.89 ± 0.04	0.30 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.01	4.92 ± 0.05	0.07 ± 0.00

Table 2. Total phenolics, flavonoids, ascorbic acid and carotenoids contents of carrot extracts prepared using different solvents

Solvent	Total phenolics content (mg GAE/g dwb)	Flavonoids content (mg CE/g dwb)	Ascorbic acid content (mg/100 g dwb)	Carotenoids content (mg/100 g dwb)
Acetone	0.55 ± 0.05	2.81 ± 0.06	7.61 ± 0.43	31.75 ± 0.98
Ethanol	1.10 ± 0.05	1.96 ± 0.06	17.02 ± 0.45	5.16 ± 0.22
Water	2.75 ± 0.10	0.88 ± 0.06	45.12 ± 0.48	0.67 ± 0.03

in acetone extract (3.46 mg/100 g fwb) followed by ethanol (0.56 mg/100 g fwb) and water (0.07 mg/100 g fwb) extracts which may be due to higher solubility of carotenoids in acetone in comparison to ethanol and water (Table 1). Similar trend was observed on dry weight basis (Table 2). Results of other research workers showed that the carotenoids content in different cultivars of carrot ranged from 0.32 to 17 mg/100 g fwb¹⁵. β -Carotene constitutes a large portion (60–80%) of the carotenoids in carrots, followed by α -carotene (10–40%), lutein (1–5%) and the other carotenoids in minor quantities (0.1–1%)⁷. Among various carotenoids, β -carotene and α -carotene which are the major carotenoids in carrots are non-polar and hence, are highly soluble in non-polar solvents¹⁷.

DPPH free radical scavenging activity :

2,2'-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) is a stable free radical (purple colour) and it transforms to non radical form (yellow colour) by abstracting one electron and hence, it is widely used as a measure for the electron donation capacity of antioxidants under assay conditions. In present studies, DPPH free radical scavenging activity (%) of the acetone, ethanol and water extracts of carrot varied widely and it increased with increase of concentration levels (Table 3). It ranged from 8.5 to 67.9% (water extract), from 3.1

and acetone extract 0.26 and 0.61 mg GAE/mL, respectively¹⁰. The water and hot water extracts of 20 commonly consumed edible mushrooms also had much higher antioxidant activities than acetone and ethanol extracts¹¹.

Antioxidant activity :

Antioxidant activity was measured by β -carotene bleaching method that is based on the ability of an antioxidant to inhibit lipid peroxidation. The mechanism of beta-carotene bleaching is a free radical-mediated phenomenon resulting from the hydroperoxides formed from linoleic acid by air oxidation. The antioxidant activity of carotenoids is based on the radical adducts of carotenoids with free radicals formed from linoleic acid. The linoleic acid free radical, formed upon the abstraction of a hydrogen atom from one of its diallylic methylene groups, attacks the highly unsaturated beta-carotene molecules. As beta-carotene molecules lose their double bonds by oxidation in this model system, in the absence of an antioxidant, the compound loses its chromophore and characteristic orange colour, which can be spectrophotometrically monitored¹⁸. In present studies, water extract of carrot (variety Hisar-Gairic) showed highest antioxidant activity (53.5%) followed by ethanol extract (52.1%) and acetone extract (41.4%) at 50 mg/mL concentration level.

Table 3. DPPH free radical scavenging activity (%) of different extracts of carrot

Extracts ↓ Conc. (mg/mL)	DPPH Free radical scavenging activity (%)						IC ₅₀ (mg/mL)
	50	25	10	5	2.5	1	
Acetone	50.3 ± 0.31	28.4 ± 0.25	11.0 ± 0.36	6.5 ± 0.47	3.7 ± 0.21	2.0 ± 0.26	47.4 ± 0.26
Ethanol	65.1 ± 0.47	36.3 ± 0.46	20.2 ± 0.26	8.9 ± 0.36	5.6 ± 0.25	3.1 ± 0.25	34.4 ± 0.32
Water	67.9 ± 0.42	65.8 ± 0.15	37.2 ± 0.47	17.7 ± 0.26	11.4 ± 0.31	8.5 ± 0.36	15.8 ± 0.36

to 65.1% (ethanol extract) and from 2.0 to 50.3% (acetone extract) at different concentration levels ranging from 1 to 50 mg/mL.

The IC₅₀ value of water extract was lowest i.e. 15.8 mg/mL followed by 34.4 mg/mL of ethanol extract and 47.4 mg/mL of acetone extract thereby showing that water extract has highest activity followed by ethanol and acetone extracts. The present findings are in agreement with the studies on Rang Chuet water extract showing highest DPPH free radical scavenging activity (EC₅₀ 0.13 mg GAE/mL) in comparison to EC₅₀ value in ethanol

Fig. 1. DPPH free radical scavenging activity (%) of different extracts of carrot at different concentration levels.

Fig. 2. Quadratic regression equations for IC_{50} values of different extracts of carrot.

The antioxidant activity of market samples of carrot collected from nearby Delhi ranged from 37.5 to 67.0% by β -carotene bleaching method¹⁹.

Experimental

Plant material and extraction :

Fresh and fully mature carrots (*Daucus carota* L.) were procured from the Research Farm of Department of Vegetable Science of CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar. Carrot variety Hisar-Gairic was taken for investigation. Carrot roots (peeled off and cut into pieces) were homogenized in Waring blender to make pulp. Ten gram of homogenized samples were extracted with 60 mL of solvents (acetone, ethanol and water) in conical flasks by shaking on a mechanical shaker for 2 h. Extracts were filtered and residues were again extracted twice (each shaking time 1 h) with 40 and 30 mL respective solvents. Filtrates of each solvent from three extraction steps were pooled and their volumes were noted. Extracts were then used for estimation of total phenolics, flavonoids, ascorbic acid contents and for evaluation of antioxidant activity.

Chemicals :

The commercially available chemicals from Sigma-Aldrich, Qualigens, Merck and Hi-Media of highest purity, were used for various experimental procedures.

Estimation of moisture content :

Moisture content was estimated by the standard procedure of AOAC²⁰. The data of moisture content was used to calculate the amount of various phytochemicals on dry weight basis (dwb).

Estimation of total phenolics content :

Total phenolics content of extracts was determined using Folin-Ciocalteu method²¹. Aliquots of 0.2 ml of extracts were mixed with 1 ml of 1 mol/L Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. After that, 2.0 ml of 20% (w/v) sodium carbonate solution was added. The solutions were mixed and volume was made up to 10.0 ml with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 730 nm using UV-Vis double beam spectrophotometer Model 2203 (Systronics Co.). A calibration curve was prepared using gallic acid as standard. Results were expressed as mg GAE/g on fresh weight as well as dry weight basis.

Estimation of flavonoids content :

Flavonoids content of extracts was estimated according to the colorimetric assay¹². In 1.0 ml of extract, 4.0 ml of double distilled water and 0.3 ml of 5% (w/v) $NaNO_2$ were added. After 5 min, 0.3 ml of 10% (w/v) $AlCl_3$ was added. Immediately, 2.0 ml of 1 M NaOH was added and the volume was made up to 10.0 ml with double distilled water. The solution was mixed thoroughly and the absorbance was measured at 510 nm using UV-Vis double beam spectrophotometer Model 2203 (Systronics Co.). A calibration curve was prepared using catechin as standard. Results were expressed as mg CE/g on fresh weight as well as dry weight basis.

Estimation of ascorbic acid content :

Ascorbic acid was estimated by titrimetric method²². 1.0 ml of each extract was taken and 5.0 ml of 2% (w/v) meta-phosphoric acid in glacial acetic acid was added. Total volume of this mixture was made up to 10.0 ml with distilled water. It was titrated against 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol dye of 10 ppm until a pink end point was obtained. Ascorbic acid content was calculated from the standard curve of ascorbic acid. Results were expressed as mg/100 g on fresh weight as well as dry weight basis.

Estimation of carotenoids content :

The extraction and estimation of carotenoids was carried out using spectrophotometric method²³. Five gram of the homogenous, representative sample was weighed and transferred to a mortar. Then it was grinded with 15 mL of cold acetone, ethanol and water each (all three refrigerated for about 3–4 h). Extract was filtered using a

Whatman filter paper and residue was again extracted twice with 5 mL of respective solvents. The filtrates were pooled together.

Forty mL petroleum ether was taken in a 500 mL separatory funnel and 25 mL extracts (acetone, ethanol and water) were added to it. 200 mL of distilled water was added by flowing along the walls of the separatory funnel to avoid formation of an emulsion. The two phases were allowed to separate and the lower aqueous phase was discarded. The petroleum ether phase was washed 3-4 times with distilled water to remove residual solvents. In the last washing the lower aqueous phase was discarded as completely as possible, without discarding any of the upper petroleum ether phase. Petroleum ether phase was collected in a 50 mL volumetric flask by making the solution passed through a small funnel containing anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove the residual water. The separatory funnel was washed with petroleum ether and the washing was collected in the volumetric flask by passing through the funnel with sodium sulphate. The volume was made up to 50 mL with petroleum ether and absorbance was measured at 450 nm. The carotenoids content was calculated using the following formula :

Carotenoids content (mg/g) =

$$\frac{A \times V \text{ (mL)} \times 10}{A_{1\text{cm}}^{1\%} \times \text{sample weight (g)}}$$

where, A = absorbance; V = total volume of extract (50 mL); $A_{1\text{cm}}^{1\%}$ = absorption coefficient of β -carotene in petroleum ether (2592).

DPPH free radical scavenging activity :

The antioxidant activity of the extracts was evaluated by 2,2'-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging method²⁴. Acetone, ethanol and water extracts were dried up completely and the weight of dry mass was noted. The dry mass of acetone and ethanol extracts was redissolved in appropriate amount of methanol to make the stock solution (50 mg/mL). Since, the dry mass of water extract was not soluble in pure methanol, hence, it was redissolved in 50% (v/v) methanol : water to make the stock solution. From stock solution, different concentrations (1-50 mg/mL) were made by appropriate dilutions with respective solvents (i.e. methanol for acetone and ethanol extracts and with methanol : water for water

extracts). For evaluation of antioxidant activity, in 0.2 mL of extracts (various concentrations), 3.0 mL of 2,2'-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical (DPPH; 0.1 mM in 100% methanol) was added and mixed thoroughly for 5 min. For antioxidant activity in water extracts (various concentrations), DPPH stock solution was prepared in 50% (v/v) methanol : water and remaining procedure was same. A control was also made containing 0.2 mL of each solvent instead of extract. The absorbance of the sample as well as control was measured at 517 nm after 30 min of incubation in dark at room temperature using the UV-Vis double beam spectrophotometer Model 2203 (Systronics Co.) against a blank containing respective solvent. Three replications were carried out for each sample. A graph was drawn by plotting per cent DPPH free radical scavenging activity (y-axis) against extract concentration (x-axis). Then using Microsoft Excel Software, quadratic regression equation ($y = ax^2 + bx + c$) was obtained and using the quadratic equation IC_{50} was calculated. The percentage of DPPH scavenged (% DPPH*_{sc}) was calculated using :

$$\%DPPH^*_{sc} = \frac{A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{control}}} \times 100$$

where, A_{control} is the absorbance of control and A_{sample} is the absorbance of the sample.

Antioxidant activity :

Antioxidant activity was measured by β -carotene bleaching method²⁵. 1.0 mg of crystalline β -carotene was dissolved in 5.0 mL of $CHCl_3$ and 0.1 mL of linoleic acid and 0.9 mL of Tween 20 (200 mg) were added. The solvent was subsequently removed at 40 °C in a vacuum evaporator and immediately the mixture was diluted with 250 mL of double distilled water. Aliquots (4 mL) of this emulsion were transferred into test tubes, to which were then added 0.2 mL of aliquots of test samples. A control containing 0.2 mL of respective solvent and 4.0 mL of emulsion was also used. The test tubes were covered with aluminium foil and placed in a water bath at 50 °C. The absorbance at 470 nm was recorded with a UV-Vis double beam spectrophotometer Model 2203 (Systronics Co.) at intervals of 30 min, until the colour of β -carotene disappeared from the control tubes. The above mixture without β -carotene served as blank. All determinations were

carried out in triplicates. The antioxidant activity was calculated using the following equation :

$$A_A(\%) = \frac{[(A_o)_{\text{control}} - (A_t)_{\text{control}}] - [(A_o)_{\text{sample}} - (A_t)_{\text{sample}}]}{[(A_o)_{\text{control}} - (A_t)_{\text{control}}]} \times 100$$

where, $(A_o)_{\text{control}}$ and $(A_o)_{\text{sample}}$ are the absorbance values measured at zero time of incubation for the control and sample, respectively and $(A_t)_{\text{control}}$ and $(A_t)_{\text{sample}}$ are the corresponding values at the end of the reaction time.

Conclusion

Results of present study shows that solvent play a vital role in the extraction of the plant constituents. Water extract of carrot contained highest total phenolic and ascorbic acid contents and also exhibited highest antioxidant activity whereas flavonoids and carotenoids contents were found to be highest in acetone extract.

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